

Legality Attentive Data Scientists Grant Agreement No. 956562

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Glossary, abbreviations and acronyms

Acronyms	Definition
CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche
EC	European Commission
ESR	Early Stage Researcher
EU	European Union
IRIT	Institut de Recherche en Informatique de Toulouse
JU	Jagiellonian University
LeADS	Legality Attentive Data Scientists
SSSA	Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna
UL	Université du Luxembourg
UPRC	University of Piraeus Research Center
UT3	Université Toulouse 3 (same as UPS)
VUB	Vrije Universiteit Brussel
WP	Work Package

Table of Contents

List of Figures.....	5
List of Photos.....	5
Executive Summary.....	6
1. Introduction.....	7
2. Video Creation.....	7
3. Video Structure and Content.....	7
4. Purpose.....	10
5. Conclusions.....	10

List of Figures

Figure 1 Visual Identification of the Project

Figure 2 Crossroads structure

List of Photos

Photo 1 ESR contributing to Crossroad 1

Photo 2 ESR contributing to Crossroad 2

Photo 3 ESR contributing to Crossroad 3

Photo 4 ESR contributing to Crossroad 4

Executive Summary

This document provides the description of the Deliverable D2.3 – Video about Crossroads, presents the structure of the Deliverable, its content, method of creation and purpose.

The deliverable D2.3 comprises of this guiding document and four-part video about Crossroads available under the link <https://vimeo.com/user/89070630/folder/16804991>

The Video about Crossroad illustrates the research areas covered by each of LeADS Crossroads. Points out their Crossroad content, development, and prospective directions.

1. Introduction

The Video about Crossroads is a deliverable being a part of WP2 Outreach and Dissemination and its purpose is the usage for the dissemination purposes within the project.

The video reflects an evolution of conducted research and scientific formation of the four main research directions - Crossroads - shaping the LeADS research content, which are:

Crossroad 1 Privacy v. Intellectual Property,

Crossroad 2 Trust in Data Processing and Algorithm Design,

Crossroad 3 Data Ownership,

Crossroad 4 Empowerment of Individuals.

The video includes compilation of fragmented interviews with LeADS ESRs conducted remotely in May-June 2023, after completion of the Second iteration of a Crossroad Report.

2. Video Creation

The process of the video production comprised of three key-stages, which were: (1) pre-production, (2) production, and (3) post-production.

- (1) Pre-production phase started in M27 and was an early planning stage, which included projecting of the video screenplay, formulating interviews questions and production planning, including establishing of technical requirements, forms and standards for recordings, and recording schedules. (M27-M28)
- (2) The production phase started in M29 and was devoted at the beginning to the collection of recordings from individual ESRs as well as recordings from group interviews with ESRs contributing to separate Crossroads. Interviews were recorded through JU's Webex platform. The collection of recordings took place until the first week of June. (M29-M30)
- (3) The post-production phase started in the second week of June and comprised of editing and selecting collected materials, adding visual and sound-effects, etc. The video was created with the use of the Vimeo platform (JU licence). (M30)

3. Video Structure and Content

The primary idea was to produce a short video (approx. 15 min.) combining all Crossroad. After collecting materials and making a pre-selection of their content we realised that the short video would be a sketchy material which would not reflect the development of the four Crossroads, not to mention their rich content.

Therefore, we decided to create one longer video containing four separate parts – one for each Crossroad. We kept the division of the video according to separate Crossroads, considering also their further dissemination and promotional usage.

The video comprises of four separate parts, one for each of Crossroads following the Crossroads structure. Video parts are available under links:

General <https://vimeo.com/user/89070630/folder/16804991>

Crossroad 1 <https://vimeo.com/user89070630/review/841260444/b48d253636>

Crossroad 2 <https://vimeo.com/user89070630/review/841260138/7604bb5f5d>

Crossroad 3 <https://vimeo.com/user89070630/review/841260324/4542a670a8>

Crossroad 4 <https://vimeo.com/user89070630/review/841262014/a0a7d9d0b9>

Each part of the video includes a visual presentation of the LeADS project, including presentation of the LeADS logo and information about EU Horizon 2020 financing (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Visual Identification of the Project

Each part of the video includes presentation of a Crossroad structure (Figure 2).

Figure 2 Crossroads structure

The content of each part is dedicated to the separate Crossroads and illustrates Crossroads’ dimensions, state-of-the-art, development of research.

The characters in each part were ESR’s attributed to each Crossroad and contributing in its development (Photos 1-4).

Photo 1 ESR contributing to Crossroad 1

Photo 2 ESR contributing to Crossroad 2

Photo 3 ESR contributing to Crossroad 3

Fatma Sumeyra DOGAN
ESR 8

Christos Magkos
ESR 11

Maciej Zuziak
ESR 6

Armend Duzha
ESR 10

Photo 4 ESR contributing to Crossroad 4

4. Purpose

The Deliverable D2.3 – Video about Crossroads is part of WP 2 focused on communication and dissemination activities.

The purpose of the Video about Crossroad is its usage for dissemination activities primarily through the LeADS communication and dissemination channels (website, youtube, linkedIn etc), but also through public presentation on Websites, in social media and via personal channels of ESRs'. The preserved division of the video in four parts gives the opportunity of sequencing the communication (presenting one after another in regular period of time) and facilitates presentation via diversified channels without necessity to implement further size adjustments. The size and format fits to most of online communication channels.

5. Conclusions

The production of the video and the result itself can be perceived from two perspectives. The most visible is a dissemination purpose, as described in section 4 above. On the one hand, the video will promote the idea of the LeADS project, the value of the EU Horizon Innovative Training Networks and the scientific content of LeADS Crossroads. On the other hand, participation in the production was also a challenge and an experience for each ESR. The task required each ESR to prepare responses to the imposed questions and present them during interviews. Therefore, this deliverable includes in it an element of hard and soft skills training.

